
Study Of Adjustment Patterns Of Secondary School Students In Relation To Emotional Maturity

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Abstract:

This study investigates the relationship between adjustment patterns and emotional maturity among secondary school students. Adjustment is a dynamic process involving the individual's effort to balance internal needs with external demands, and emotional maturity plays a crucial role in shaping this ability. The research aims to examine how emotional, social, and educational adjustment differ across gender and varying levels of emotional maturity. A sample of 100 students (50 boys and 50 girls) from urban areas of Pathankot district was selected. Standardized tools measuring adjustment and emotional maturity were administered, and data were analysed using statistical techniques including t-tests, ANOVA, and correlation. It identified the gender differences in adjustment and emotional maturity, exploring relationships between emotional maturity levels and types of adjustment, and understanding the overall connection between emotional maturity and school adjustment. The findings revealed significant associations between emotional maturity and various aspects of adjustment, emphasizing the importance of fostering emotional development in students to enhance their personal, academic, and social functioning.

Keywords: *Adjustment Patterns, Emotional Maturity, Secondary School Students Emotional Adjustment, Social Adjustment, Educational Adjustment.*

Introduction:

Education is the transmission of knowledge, skills, and character traits and manifests in various forms. Generally, education conceived as a process or methods of learning and training that the whole of human personality in different dimension. It modifies man's experience, transforms his instinctive urges and impulses and determines his attitude and beliefs. Education enables man to draw out his hidden talents. It trains him to increase his productivity and thus it helps him to render more effective service to society. The basic purpose lying at the very root of every plan and programme of education is to bring about in the human being the

changes, which are conducive to proper growth of the learner into full-fledged responsible citizens. Different philosophers, educationists, thinkers, statesman, politician, merchants, artisans and priests have given different definitions of education from time to time. The reason is that though education seems to be an abstract entity, its concept is dynamic. It has passed through many ages and stages in the process of evolution and at every stage it has had a different meaning according to the conditions then prevailing. Being dynamic in nature, the concept of education is always in the process of evolution that may never come to an end. It must continuously grow and change as ever.

Many factors influence the success of education. Psychological factors include motivation, intelligence, and personality. Social factors, such as socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and gender, are often associated with discrimination. Other factors encompass access to educational technology, teacher quality, and parental involvement.. One essential and binding feature of human relationship is to be a man of culture. A man of culture is an individual asset to society.

Concept of Adjustment:

The concept of adjustment was initially a biological one and was a corner stone in Darwin's theory of evolution (1859). In Biology, the term usually employed was an adaptation. Darwin maintained that only those organisms most fitted to adapt to the hazards of the physical world survive. Biologists have continued to be concerned with the problem of biological adaptations, and much of human illness is based on transformation to the stress of life. In psychology, adjustment refers to the behavioural process of balancing conflicting needs or needs challenged by obstacles in the environment. Humans and animals regularly adjust to their environment. For example, when their physiological state stimulates them to seek food, they eat (if possible) to reduce their hunger and adapt to the hunger stimulus. Adjustment disorder occurs when there is an inability to make a standard adjustment to some need or stress in the environment. The adjustment has been analysed as an achievement and a process in psychology.

Concept of Emotional Maturity:

In the present circumstances, youth as well as children are facing difficulties in life. These difficulties are giving rise to

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many psycho-somatic problems such as anxiety, tensions, frustrations and emotional upsets in day to day life. So, the study of emotional life is now emerging as a descriptive science, comparable with anatomy. It deals with interplay of forces with intensities and quantities. Kaplan and Baron (1986) elaborated the characteristic of an emotionally nature person that he has the capacity to with stand delay in satisfaction of needs. Actually, emotional maturity is not only the effective determine of personality pattern but it also helps to control the growth of adolescent's development. The concept "Mature" emotional behaviour of any level is that which reflects the fruits of normal emotional development. A person who is able to keep his emotions under control, which is able to break delay and to suffer without self-pity, might still be emotionally stunned and childish. The most outstanding mark of emotional maturity, according to Cole (1980) is ability to bear tension.

Review of Related Literature:

Arya (1984) conducted a study for emotional maturity and value of superior children in family. The objectives of the study were to found relationship between intelligence and emotional maturity of boys and girls separately. Second objective was to find out relationship between intelligence and values of boys and girls. The study find that superior boys and girls do well on the emotional maturity tests, superior intelligence showed high relationship with emotional maturity.

Kaur (1995) conducted a study on the impact of attitudes of violence and non-violence on the levels of emotional maturity and adjustment patterns of college going students. She found that most of the college going girls are more emotionally stable as compared to college going boy students. She also summarized that

'emotional maturity is the ability to govern disturbing emotions.'

Chauhan and Sharma (1997) conducted a study to measure the feeling of insecurity, emotional maturity, creative thinking and vocational interests of the girl child laborers. They concluded that there is no significant difference in the emotional maturity of girl child laborers and the normal ones.

Adhikari (1998) studied the difference in emotional maturity between University students and University teachers in India. 200 male and 200 female University students and 150 male and 150 female University teachers were administered a Hindi version of the Swamulyanka Prashnawali by R.R. Tripathi and Rastogi (1982). The emotional maturity scores of male teachers and females teachers were higher than those of the students.

Martin, Chemers and Garcia (2001) examined the effects of academic self efficacy that is confidence in ability to perform well academically, optimism, and stress on the academic performance and adjustment of first year university students. The sample was composed of 256 first year students. Result indicated that self-efficacy yielded of direct and indirect powerful relationships with academic performance and adjustment of first year college students. Optimism was also found to be related to academic performance adjustment. Academically confident and optimistic students were more likely to see the university experience as a challenger rather than a threat and they experienced less stress.

Wilton and Constantine (2003) examined cultural adjustment and psychological distress issues in 190 Asian and Latin American international college students. Findings revealed that Latin American students reported higher levels of psychological distress than did their Asian peers. Moreover, length of residence in the

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U.S. was negatively associated with psychological distress symptoms, and acculturative distress and intercultural competence concerns were positively related to psychological distress in both groups.

Justification of the Problem:

In this present study at the secondary level, Emotional maturity in relation to School adjustment among the students is very important, which helps him or them in the adjustment process and helps them excel in the academic field. It has been observed that very little study has been done in this area, especially in the Pathankot district and surrounding areas in Punjab state. In this context, the investigator has felt for doing this study. The study aims to find out the Emotional maturity and School adjustment of secondary school students. And the present study entitled "Emotional Maturity, in relation to School Adjustment of Secondary School Students."

Statement of the Problem:

Study of Adjustment Patterns of Secondary School Students In Relation To Emotional Maturity

Delimitations of the Study:

1. The study was delimited to 100 students both boys and girls of 9th class only.
2. The study was delimited to schools situated in urban area of Pathankot district only.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender.
 - (a) To study Emotional Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to Gender.

- (b) To study Social Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to Gender.
- (c) To study Educational Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to Gender.
2. To study Emotional Maturity among secondary school students with respect to Gender.
- (a) To study Emotional Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity.
- (b) To study Social Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity.
- (c) To study Educational Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity.
3. To study relationship of Emotional Adjustment and Emotional Maturity of secondary school students.
4. To study relationship of Social Adjustment and Emotional Maturity of secondary school students.
5. To study relationship of Educational Adjustment and Emotional Maturity of secondary school students.

Hypotheses of the Study:

1. There exists no significant difference in Adjustment patterns among secondary school students with respect to Gender.
- (a) There exists no significant difference in Emotional Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to Gender.
- (b) There exists no significant difference in Social Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to Gender.
- (c) There exists no significant difference in Educational Adjustment of Secondary School students with respect to Gender.

2. There exists no significant difference in Emotional Maturity among secondary school students with respect to Gender.
- (a). There exists no significant difference in Emotional Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity.
- (b). There exists no significant difference in Social Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity.
- (c). There exists no significant difference in Educational Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity.
3. There exists no significant relationship Emotional Adjustment and Emotional Maturity of secondary school students.
4. There exists no significant relationship of Social Adjustment and Emotional Maturity of secondary school students.
5. There exists no significant relationship of Educational Adjustment and Emotional Maturity of secondary school students.

Research Design:

The present investigation is concerned with Emotional maturity with Adjustment patterns of Secondary school students. The main purpose of the study is to measure these two psychological variables of the school students of 9th class and to also make comparison of the different aspects and dimensions of Emotional Maturity and Adjustment patterns between boys and girls students of urban school students. It is an attempt to establish the relationship between Emotional maturity and Adjustment inventory.

Sampling:

The population for the study is secondary school students of Pathankot district. A sample of 100 students of secondary classes were selected randomly; out of which 50 will be boys students and 50 girls students. The students from urban area schools were taken. The standardized test is distributed to students

Tools of the Study:

Tool 1. Emotional Maturity Scale by Yashvir Singh & Mahesh Bhargava, 2012.

Tool 2. Adjustment Patterns Scale by A.K.P Singh & R.P Singh, 2007.

Statistical Techniques:

For hypothesis testing, data analysis was made employing descriptive statistics such as, Mean, Standard Deviation, 't'- test and Pearson coefficient correlation.

Hypotheses No.1

Hypothesis-I was framed to examine the significant difference in Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. To test the hypotheses, Mean, SD & t-test was applied to determine the significant difference of Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. The result of the hypotheses has been reported in table

1

TABLE 1: MEAN, SD AND T-SCORE OF ADJUSTMENT PATTERNS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Adjustment	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remarks
	Male	50	14.40	5.368	98	.188	Significant at 0. 05 Level
	Female	50	14.62	6.289			

Table 1 shows that the mean and SD of males of secondary schools are 14.40 and 5.368 and females of secondary schools are 14.62 and 6.289 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t- value is .188 greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level. So, our null hypotheses " There exists no significant difference in Adjustment patterns among secondary school students with respect to Gender.", was rejected at the 0.5 level of significance.

Hypotheses No. I (a):

Hypothesis-I (a) was framed to examine the significant difference in Emotional Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. To test the hypotheses, Mean, SD & t-test was applied to determine the significant difference of Emotional Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. The result of the hypotheses has been reported in table

2

TABLE 2: MEAN, SD AND T-SCORE OF EMOTIONAL ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Emotional Adjustment	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remarks
	Male	50	5.12	2.987	98	.791	Significant at 0. 05 Level
	Female	50	4.62	3.325			

Table 2 shows that the mean and SD of males of secondary schools are 5.12 and 2.987 and females of secondary schools are 4.62 and 3.325 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t- value is .791

greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level. So, our null hypotheses "There exists no significant difference in emotional Adjustment of secondary school students

with respect to Gender", was rejected at the .05 level of significance.

Hypotheses II(b):

Hypothesis-II (b) was framed to examine the significant difference in Social Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. To

test the hypotheses, Mean, SD & t-test was applied to determine the significant difference of Social Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. The result of the hypotheses has been reported in table 3.

TABLE 3: MEAN, SD AND T-SCORE OF SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Social Adjustment	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remarks
	Male	50	6.06	2.606			
	Female	50	6.24	2.421			

Table 3 shows that the mean and SD of males of secondary schools are 6.06 and 2.606 and females of secondary schools are 6.24 and 2.421 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t- value is .358 greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level. So, our null hypotheses "There exists no significant difference in social adjustment of secondary school students with respect to gender", was rejected at the .05level of significance.

Hypotheses No. II(c):

Hypothesis-II (c) was framed to examine the significant difference in Educational Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. To test the hypotheses, Mean, SD & t-test was applied to determine the significant difference of Educational Adjustment patterns of secondary school students with respect to Gender. The result of the hypotheses has been reported in table 4

TABLE 4: MEAN, SD AND T-SCORE OF EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Educational Adjustment	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remarks
	Male	50	3.22	1.810			
	Female	50	3.76	2.291			

Table 4 shows that the mean and SD of males of secondary schools are 3.22 and 1.810 and females of secondary schools are 3.76 and 2.291 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t- value is 1.308 greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level. So, our null hypotheses "There exists no significant difference in educational adjustment of secondary school students with respect to gender", was therefore rejected at the .05level of significance.

Hypotheses No. II

Hypothesis-II was framed to examine the significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students with respect to Gender. To test the hypotheses, Mean, SD & t-test was applied to determine the significant difference of emotional maturity of secondary school students with respect to Gender. The result of the hypotheses has been reported in table 5

TABLE 5 : MEAN, SD AND T-SCORE OF EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Emotional Maturity	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remarks
	Male	50	98.48	22.809	98	.619	Significant at 0.05 level
	Female	50	95.74	21.439			

Table 5 shows that the mean and SD of males of secondary schools are 98.48 and 22.809 and females of secondary schools are 95.74 and 21.439 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t-value is .619 greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level. So, our null hypotheses "There exists no significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students with respect to gender", was rejected at the 0.5 level of significance.

Hypothesis No. II (a):

There exists no significant difference in Emotional Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity. To test the hypothesis, one way analysis of variance was applied to determine the significant difference between emotional adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity. The result of this analysis has been reported in table 6

TABLE 6: MEANS OF SUB-GROUPS OF ANOVA FOR 2×2 DESIGN ON THE SCORES OF EMOTIONAL ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO DIFFERENT LEVELS OF EMOTIONAL MATURITY

Emotional Adjustment	Levels of Emotional Maturity	N	Mean	SD
	High	27	4.26	3.071
	Average	49	5.24	3.301
	Low	24	4.79	2.949
	Total	100	4.87	3.155

Table 7: t-value of Emotional Adjustment Scores of Secondary School Students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity

	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	t-value	F	Remarks
Between Groups	2	17.105	8.553	4.99	.857	Significant at 0.05 level
Within Groups	97	968.205	9.981			
Total	99	985.310				

The table 7 reveals that calculated t-value 4.99 was found to be greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. So, it reveals that there is a significant difference in emotional adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity. Therefore, our null hypothesis "There exists no significant difference in

emotional Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity", was therefore rejected at the .05 level of significance. Further examination of means of all the groups (table 4.6) reveals that high emotionally mature group is most adjusted at emotional level and low emotionally immature is least adjusted.

Hypothesis No. II(b)

There exists no significant difference in Social Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity. To test the hypothesis, one way analysis of

variance was applied to determine the significant difference between social adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity. The result of this analysis has been reported in table 8

TABLE 8: MEANS OF SUB-GROUPS OF ANOVA FOR 2×2 DESIGN ON THE SCORES OF SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO DIFFERENT LEVELS OF EMOTIONAL MATURITY

	Levels of Emotional Maturity	N	Mean	SD
Social Adjustment	High	27	5.78	2.577
	Average	49	6.39	2.290
	Low	24	6.08	2.873
	Total	100	6.15	2.504

Table 9: t-value of Social Adjustment Scores of Secondary School Students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	t-value	F	Remarks
Between Groups	6.617	2	3.309	2.67	.523	Significant at 0.05 level
Within Groups	614.133	97	6.331			
Total	620.750	99				

The table 9 reveals that calculated t-value 2.67 was found to be greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. So, it reveals that there is a significant difference in emotional adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity. Therefore, our null hypothesis "There exists no significant difference in social Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity", was therefore rejected at the .05 level of significance.

Further examination of means of all the groups (table 4.6) reveals that high

emotionally mature group is most adjusted at emotional level and low emotionally immature is least adjusted

Hypothesis No. II(c)

There exists no significant difference in Educational Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity. To test the hypothesis, one way analysis of variance was applied to determine the significant difference between educational adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity. The result of this analysis has been reported in table 10.

Table 10: Means Of Sub-Groups Of Anova For 2×2 Design On The Scores Of Educational Adjustment Of Secondary School Students With Respect To Different Levels Of Emotional Maturity

	Levels of Emotional Maturity	N	Mean	SD
EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT	High	27	3.37	1.864
	Average	49	3.69	2.426
	Low	24	3.21	1.444
	Total	100	3.49	2.072

TABLE 11: t-value of Educational Adjustment Scores of Secondary School Students with respect to different levels of Emotional Maturity

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	t-value	F	Remarks
Between Groups	4.327	2	2.164	3.56	.499	Significant at 0.05 level
Within Groups	420.663	97	4.337			
Total	424.990	99				

The table 11 reveals that calculated t-value 3.56 was found to be greater than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. So, it reveals that there is a significant difference in educational adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity. Therefore, our null hypothesis "There exists no significant difference in Educational Adjustment of secondary school students with respect to different levels of emotional maturity", was therefore rejected at the .05 level of significance.

Further examination of means of all the groups (table 11) reveals that high

emotionally mature group is most adjusted at emotional level and low emotionally immature is least adjusted

Hypothesis No. III

Hypothesis-III was framed to examine the significant relationship between Emotional Adjustment and emotional maturity. To test the hypothesis, Pearson correlation was applied to determine the significant relationship between emotional adjustment and emotional maturity of secondary school students. The result of this analysis has been reported in table

TABLE 12 : SHOWING CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL ADJUSTMENT AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

		Emotional Adjustment
Emotional Maturity	Pearson Correlation	.081
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.425
	N	100

From the calculations, we concluded that co-efficient of correlation (r) = .081. The table no. 4.9 indicates that adjustment was significantly correlated with ($r = .081$ significant at .005 level). Thus, the null hypothesis stating that "There exists no significant relationship between emotional adjustment and emotional maturity of secondary school students", was therefore rejected at the 0.05 level of significance, which shows the positive correlation between Emotional Maturity and Emotional Adjustment. So, the results of the study conclude that emotionally matured person can adjust at the emotional level very effectively.

Hypotheses No. IV

Hypothesis-IV was framed to examine the significant relationship between Social adjustment and emotional maturity. To test the hypothesis, Pearson correlation was applied to determine the significant relationship between social adjustment and emotional maturity of secondary school students. The result of this analysis has been reported in table 13.

TABLE 13: SHOWING CORRELATION BETWEEN SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY

		Social Adjustment
Emotional Maturity	Pearson Correlation	.044
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.664
	N	100

From the calculations, we concluded that co-efficient of correlation (r) = .044. The table no. 4.10 indicates that adjustment was significantly correlated with ($r = .044$ significant at .005 level). Thus, the null hypothesis stating that "There exists no significant relationship between social adjustment and emotional maturity of secondary school students", was therefore rejected at the 0.05 level of significance, which shows the positive correlation between Emotional Maturity and Social Adjustment. So, the results of the study conclude that emotionally

matured person can adjust at the emotional level very effectively.

Hypothesis No. V

Hypothesis-V was framed to examine the significant relationship between Educational Adjustment and emotional maturity. To test the hypothesis, Pearson correlation was applied to determine the significant relationship between educational adjustment and emotional maturity of secondary school students. The result of this analysis has been reported in table 14

TABLE 14: SHOWING CORRELATION BETWEEN EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY

		Educational Adjustment
Emotional Maturity	Pearson Correlation	.087
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.387
	N	100

From the calculations, we concluded that co-efficient of correlation (r) = .087. The table no. 14 indicates that adjustment was significantly correlated with ($r = .087$ significant at .005 level). Thus, the null hypothesis stating that "There exists no significant relationship between Educational Adjustment and emotional maturity of secondary school students", was therefore rejected at the 0.05 level of significance, which shows the positive correlation between Emotional Maturity and Educational Adjustment. So, the results of the study conclude that emotionally matured person can adjust at the emotional level very effectively.

Educational Implications:

1. Teachers should encourage open communication and active listening for emotional maturity among students.
2. Activities like role playing, group discussions and reflective writing should be encouraged by teachers to develop emotional maturity among students.
3. Teachers should recognize diverse adjustment patterns and give personalized support.
4. Teachers should promote respect, trust, and a sense of belonging.
5. Schools should include programs that build resilience, stress

management, empathy, and conflict resolution skills

6. Activities like group projects, discussions, and peer tutoring foster healthy peer relationships.
7. Regular guidance services help students handle personal, social, or academic issues.
8. Students with adjustment difficulties may benefit from differentiated instruction, remedial help, and fair assessments.
9. Less rigid academic expectations can reduce stress for poorly adjusted students.
10. Encouraging participation builds self-confidence and teamwork skills.

Conclusion:

From whole study, concluded that emotional maturity effects on different dimensions of adjustment patterns of students in school. The boys of secondary school had less adjustment than girls . However, there was a significant interaction effect of different dimensions adjustment patterns and emotional maturity. Interrelation between Adjustment and Emotional Maturity.A strong positive correlation was found between emotional maturity and all three aspects of adjustment. This emphasizes the importance of emotional development in the holistic well-being and academic performance of students.

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